

ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ,
ФАН ВА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ВАЗИРЛИГИ

ТОШКЕНТ КИМЁ ХАЛҚАРО УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ

“XXI АСР ТАРЖИМАШУНОСЛИГИНИНГ ЛИНГВОМАДАНИЙ МАСАЛАЛАРИ” ХАЛҚАРО ИЛМИЙ-НАЗАРИЙ АНЖУМАН

Тўплами

華僑大學
HUAQIAO UNIVERSITY

Тошкент ш., Ўзбекистон
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THE IMPORTANCE OF RESEARCH COMPETENCE

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Abstract

This article uses the words competence and competency-based approach to investigate the relevance of competency-based methods in the country of Uzbekistan. Also, it places an emphasis on the fundamental skills that must be possessed by those who teach foreign languages. In addition to this, the article cites earlier works that have been published on the issue and offers definitions of research competencies for authors. In the last section of the paper, a discussion of the pedagogical support for the development of skills based on "pre-service" and "in-service" programs is presented.

Key words: competence, competence-based approach, "pre-service" programs, "in-service" programs.

Introduction. Competency-based higher education depends on the development of general and specific skills. Teaching foreign languages requires linguistic, psychological-pedagogical, and professional-methodological abilities. Researchers are subject to the same standards of competence regardless of their major area of expertise. It may also be part of a teacher's linguistic, professional, methodological, and pedagogical abilities, depending on their specialty. This may occur in several situations.

Literature review. The expert's expertise requires study to develop and apply. The potential expert is now ready to work. Higher education prepares future researchers. Students and teachers in fundamental research will foster new ideas and academics. Scholars found that research is vital for society's progress. Higher education institutions globally value research [1]. So, higher education must develop research skills in future professions.

Research competence involves doing independent research and communicating its findings [2]. Research competency is the foundation of professional, methodological, cultural, and general competency growth [3].

A.Kh. Makhmudov defined "competence" as "a person's integrative quality (socio-psychological component), encompassing special aspects of interrelated and mutually impacting integrative knowledge, abilities, and qualifications (cognitive component), as well as socially meaningful attributes (readiness for decisions, suitability and responsibility)" [4].

Foreign language instructors need more than only the CEFR-listed skills. Pedagogical competence helps potential teachers arrange courses, solve issues, develop activities, be creative and adaptive, comprehend students, enhance their speech, inspire them, include them in all sorts of activities regardless of capacity, and listen in an audience [5].

Research Methodology. Our survey identified the following qualities as crucial for prospective educators: General competences: Declarative knowledge; Practical expertise; Existentialism; Learnability Communication: Linguistic; Sociolinguistic; Pragmatic; Skills: Assessment competence (self-assessment); ICT competence (digital); Educational competence; Professional competence; Appropriate humor; Change competence; Studying abroad and teacher competency; Research, curriculum, and lifelong learning.

Analysis and results. Action research improves pre-service teachers' research and reflection skills [6]. Hence, action research helps prospective instructors evaluate their teaching techniques [7]. We made practical suggestions for developing prospective foreign language instructors' general and communicative language skills based on the "pre-service" and "in-service" programs.

Conclusion. Research competency transforms a teacher from a spectator into a change agent who not only repeats existing techniques of education but also searches out and implements new technologies and processes. Teachers gain from seminars, conferences, professional organization meetings, and professional publications because of their focused investigation. This lets instructors learn from others and themselves. So, the method for improving pre-service teachers' research abilities is a reliable tool for ensuring continual personal and professional growth and improving English education nationwide.

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